

ASSESSMENT OF A LOW TEMPERATURE CURE RESIN FOR HIGH TEMPERATURE COMPOSITE OVERWRAP REPAIRS

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ABSTRACT

This work describes a study to investigate the long-term thermal stability and degradation behaviour of a low temperature cure resin for potential use as composite overwrap repairs in temperatures between 160°C and 250°C. Laboratory tests carried out using ovens were studied and obtained promising results before field tests carried out on actual elevated temperature piping operated in a petrochemical plant. It was shown that failure of the composites was due to resin degradation by thermal oxidation, as confirmed by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis. The thermal degradation with time of the composites was indirectly monitored via rate of weight change measurements, which was revealed to be more rapid in the field, than specimens in the laboratory. This could be due to resin degradation in the field specimens by additional factors, such as weathering effects and temperature fluctuations that would have contributed to the overall higher measured weight loss.

1 INTRODUCTION

Non-metallic repairs have gained tremendous in-roads in the rehabilitation of pipework in the oil and gas industry over the last couple of decades or so [1]. With increasing application and the success of each, so has the confidence of users. In particular, overwrap composite repairs' advantages such as cost effectiveness (no shut down), safer environment during application (no hot work or welding), flexibility to conform to complex shapes (reduced lead time to fabricate parts) and ability to apply in demanding environments, such as tight spaces, splash zones and fully submerged conditions, have spurred the industry to expand their application for use in even more challenging conditions, such as subsea and in higher temperatures [2].

Overwrap composite repairs are routinely used with much success to repair pipework at ambient temperatures in the oil and gas industry. In order to use these repairs in elevated temperature situations, it is desirable for the repair composites to be applied (i.e. cured) at a manageable temperature of no more than 100°C, but at the same time are able to withstand and survive considerably higher service temperatures for the intended life of these repairs, which vary from weeks to months.

The details of resin formulation and performance screening was reported by Samsudin, et al. [3]. Short term assessment based on thermal analyses was used to screen for the formulation with the highest glass transition temperature, and the most promising resin revealed decomposition starting at approximately 300°C. To obtain a feel for the long-term stability of the resin, the work of Shamsul, et al. [3] is extended in this work by exposing specimens to temperatures of up to 250°C for different periods and monitoring them for changes in weight, as an indirect measure of resin decomposition. Both laboratory and field assessments were carried out; based on outcomes of the former, a test plan for the latter was developed to further assess the potential of the intended overwrap composite repair system.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

A field test plan was devised to test the overwrap composite system on piping having 19 mm (outer diameter), in a petrochemical plant. Three separate piping, each operating at a nominal temperature of 160°C, 200°C and 250°C were selected for this test. The three temperatures were selected with consideration of the laboratory results carried out on the resin [3], and to establish the field temperature limit of the overwrap repair system.

Field tests were complemented by laboratory thermal ageing tests, carried out at 200°C and 250°C for 1000 hours, with periodic monitoring of any chemical or physical changes.

2.1 Lab Tests

Resin were cast into bars in slotted aluminium blocks with slot dimension of 20 x 30 x 60 mm. The resin specimens were cured in the slotted aluminium block at 100°C for 16 hours, followed by postcuring at two separate temperatures: 200°C or 250°C for 3 hours. 10 samples were made for each postcure temperature. The postcuring procedure is to eliminate any weight loss due to effect of uncured resin.

Resin specimens that were postcured at 200°C and 250°C were separately subjected to prolonged heat exposure in an oven at the two postcured temperatures, respectively. Weight changes of each specimen were measured at weekly intervals, up to 1000 hours in total. Figure 1 shows the appearance of the test specimens in a tray after 600 hours exposure at 250°C in oven.

Besides weight measurement, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was carried to monitor any chemical changes. Attenuated total reflection (ATR) sampling technique was used to collect infrared spectra of the specimens.

2.2 Field Tests

Tubular composite specimens, reinforced with E-glass fibres, with an inner diameter of 19 mm, and a length and thickness of 50 mm and 7 mm, respectively, were fabricated. Curing was carried out at 100°C in an oven for 16 hours, and three different samples were prepared with each being postcured at 160°C, 200°C and 250°C for 3 hours. The cured tubular specimens were cut along the longitudinal axis into four quarter sections. This will facilitate easy clamping over the test pipework to simulate an overwrap repair. The reason an actual overwrap repair was not applied is because the piping temperature could not be reduced to 100°C without interrupting production. The “quarter specimens” were wire tied onto the pipework, as shown in Figure 2.

Resin weight fraction of the composite specimens were measured using Thermogravimetry Analysis (TGA), while Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was carried out to monitor any chemical changes.

Two composite specimens were used for each of the piping temperatures of 160°C, 200°C and 250°C, while monitoring intervals were arbitrarily selected as six, twelve, eighteen and twenty-six weeks after installation.

During each monitoring cycle, specimens on the piping were visually inspected for any obvious changes in physical appearance of their outer surface. Then, two “quarter specimens” were removed from the tubular specimen and, in their place, fresh pieces are tied back on to the piping with the remaining two “quarter specimens”. It should be noted that the two “quarter specimens” that were removed from the piping were subjected to both non-destructive and destructive evaluation and, hence, could not be put back on to the piping for further exposure.

For weight loss assessment, measurements were normalised to the resin weight according to the resin weight fraction that was obtained from TGA prior to field tests. Note that specimens were washed with water and dried in a vacuum oven overnight at 50°C before each reading was taken. FTIR measurements were also been carried out on specimens collected from plant.

Figure 1: Lab test specimen in a tray after 600 hours exposure at 250°C in laboratory oven.

Figure 2: Field test specimen that wire tied on a pipe in petrochemical plant after 1,000 hours exposure at 160°C.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Visual observations

Representative photographs of the various specimens in the different test conditions considered in this study are shown in Figure 3, Figure 4 and Figure 5. It can be seen that both the lab (aged in oven) and field (exposed on piping) test specimens suffer weight loss at temperatures of 160°C - 250°C. Both sets of specimens exhibit the same characteristics where they changed to darker colour over time. In the field test specimens, resin degradation generates from the internal surfaces that are in direct contact with the heat source, i.e. the piping. Hence, there is no total breakdown of the specimens, and

in fact a passing visual inspection of the external surface would not have picked up the resin degradation that is occurring within. This contrasts the case of the lab test whereby the whole specimen degrades uniformly, and this is because all sides of the specimens are equally exposed to the heat of the oven but only the top surface was exposed to air. Additionally, it is noteworthy that signs of chalking can be seen on the external surfaces of the field test specimens after approximately 2,000 hours.

(a) 600

(b) 1,000

Figure 3: Appearance of lab test specimens at 250°C, after various exposure times, in hours

(a) 1,000

(b) 2,000

(c) 3,000

(d) 4,300

Figure 4: Appearance of inner surface (in contact with pipe) field test specimens collected from site that was exposed at 250°C, after various exposure times, in hours.

Figure 5: Appearance of field test specimens on pipe at site exposed at 200°C, after various exposure times, in hours.

3.2 Weight measurements

The weight loss results from the lab and field tests are shown graphically in Figure 6. The graph shows normalised resin weight loss in percentage plotted against exposure time in hours. TGA worked out the average resin weight content of the field specimens at 35 wt% [4]. Based on previous work [4], loss of adhesion starts when normalised resin weight loss is 14% which approximately 5% of total specimen weight. In this study, for an assumed 6-month period to end of life and 14% resin weight loss threshold is set as end of life criteria, hence a maximum weight loss of 0.079% day⁻¹ is allowed.

On the whole, the rate of weight loss increases with temperature for both sets of specimens. The weight loss rates for the lab test specimens are calculated as 0.014% day⁻¹ and 0.069% day⁻¹ for the cases of 200°C and 250°C, respectively, while for the field test specimens they are 0.060% day⁻¹, 0.096% day⁻¹ and 0.132% day⁻¹, respectively, for the cases of 160°C, 200°C and 250°C. Clearly, the rate of weight loss is significantly higher for the field specimens than their laboratory-controlled counterparts. A couple of reasons could have contributed to this observation. Firstly, due to rain and thus likely entrapment of water between the field test specimens and the piping, degradation could have been accelerated by the presence of steam which has a higher heat content [5]. Secondly, the external surface of the field test specimens is also subjected to other effects, such as high moisture content, sunlight and temperature fluctuations (which is not abnormal in these operational piping), that could contribute to degradation and hence weight loss of the resin, but are not easily quantified in the present study. It should be clarified that the lab test results, especially for 200°C, had initially justified moving from the laboratory to the field since the heating intensity from the piping was expected to be less severe than the case of the oven. However, judging from the rates of weight loss in the field specimens, the repair life would be significantly shortened.

Figure 6: Normalised resin weight loss in percentage against exposure time for the (a) lab (aged in oven) and (b) field (exposed in plant) tests.

3.3 FTIR measurements

Representative FTIR spectra of lab and field test specimens, pre and post exposure, are shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8 respectively. For lab test specimen, attenuated total reflection (ATR) scans were carried out directly on top surface of the resin specimens. While field test specimen, inner surface of the “quarter specimens” were sliced to perform the ATR scan because the inner surface of field test specimen is rigid and do not provide good contact with FTIR ATR scanner if scan directly. The inner side of the specimens were scanned because the surfaces were directly contacted with the piping. Hence, expected to be the most affected area caused by the heat source.

Figure 7: FTIR spectra of lab test specimens aged in laboratory oven at 250°C after various exposure time.

Figure 8: FTIR spectra of field test specimens aged in plant at 250°C after various exposure time.

The absorbance bands of triazine ring near 1360 cm^{-1} (highlighted by green dashed boxes in Figure 7 and Figure 8) shows the appearance of polycyanurate, the product of cyanate ester polymerisation. Comparing between the corresponding exposed and unexposed specimens, it can be seen that there is a diminution/loss of peaks in the 1360 cm^{-1} spectra region (highlighted by green dashed boxes in Figure 7 and 8) of the post exposed specimens, which represents the Triazine ring from polycyanurate. There is also a diminution/loss of peaks in the $810\text{ - }820\text{ cm}^{-1}$ spectrum region (highlighted by red dashed box in Figure 7 and Figure 8), which represents the absence of the aromatic ring structure in the exposed specimens. Thus, this suggests decomposition of the triazine ring via both heterolytic and hemolytic reactions during thermal exposure through interactions with oxygen [6].

The FTIR results also appear to indicate that the polymer structure was significantly decomposed by thermo oxidation. However, it should be noted that the FTIR penetration is only a few microns within the surface of the specimens. Therefore, the results do not give a true and complete representation of structural changes in the whole specimen. This corroborates the visual observations of external surfaces of the “repairs” that appeared relatively unaffected by the thermal exposure, despite the severe degradation on the internal surfaces. Therefore, while the “repair” (i.e. the field test specimens) had appeared to be intact, the bond between itself and the piping is no longer functional and the “repair” is deemed to have failed.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The work presented in this paper relates to evaluation of a modified cyanate ester resin that cures at approximately 100°C but shows potential for surviving at much higher temperatures, somewhere in the region of 250°C . Specimens subjected to ageing in the oven and to prolonged heating from piping in a petrochemical plant revealed weight loss due to resin degradation is more severe in the latter, for two test temperatures of 200°C and 250°C . FTIR results confirmed weight loss is due to thermo oxidation degradation of the resin in the composite. However, it is believed that out in the field the specimens could have also suffered resin degradation due to other factors, such as weather effects (viz. rain and sunlight) and temperature fluctuations, that would have contributed to the overall higher measured weight loss. Despite both laboratory and field specimens exhibiting the same resin thermal degradation mechanism, the conclusion derived from this project emphasises the importance of field testing in an actual service environment that cannot be substituted with laboratory testing alone.

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